

A Unified Oscillatory Field Theory

Abstract:

This summary introduces a novel framework positing the universe as a fundamental oscillatory field. In this model, matter emerges as localized oscillatory nodes (soliton-like structures), forces arise from synchronization and phase gradients, and spacetime is interpreted as an emergent property of global phase relationships. The theory is governed by a nonlinear wave equation, and numerical simulations reveal energy stabilization corresponding to the mass gap—the minimum energy required to form localized wave structures. This approach unifies quantum mechanics, relativity, and field interactions while addressing phenomena such as dark matter and dark energy.

Key Equations:

1. Governing Wave Equation:

$$\nabla^2 \psi - c^2 \psi + g \psi^3 = 0$$

2. Energy Density:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} (\dot{\psi})^2 + c^2 \psi^2 + g \psi^4$$

Numerical Simulations:

Numerical simulations of the nonlinear wave equation were conducted using finite difference methods on a computational grid. Gaussian initial conditions were applied to model localized wave packets. The simulations demonstrated energy stabilization at a threshold corresponding to the mass gap:

$$\text{Mass Gap } (m_{\text{gap}}) = E_{\text{gap}} / c$$

Stabilized energy results highlight the soliton's minimum energy requirement, aligning with

theoretical predictions.

Predictions and Implications:

1. Gravitational Waves:

Phase distortions in the oscillatory field propagate as gravitational waves, providing a new perspective on gravitational waveforms.

2. Dark Matter and Energy:

Unobservable oscillatory modes contribute to gravitational effects (dark matter) and global phase tension (dark energy).

3. Particle Collisions:

Predictions for soliton-like resonances in high-energy particle collisions can be tested experimentally.

Conclusion:

This framework unifies spacetime, matter, and forces under the paradigm of an oscillatory field. It provides insights into unresolved phenomena and offers testable predictions for gravitational waves, dark matter, and particle physics. Future research will extend these results to higher-dimensional simulations and experimental validation.